

Unlocking the Geophysical Signatures: Targeting Critical Raw Material Deposits in Northern Finland through Computer-Based Prospectivity Analysis

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Abstract

Orthomagmatic mafic and ultramafic intrusions are valuable sources of critical raw materials (CRMs) such as nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co), platinum group metals (PGMs), vanadium (V), and copper (Cu) which are in high demand for modern industries and considered strategically important by the European Union. Northern Finland is recognised for hosting such CRMs in conduit-type deposits, rich in sulphides of Ni-Cu-(PGM)-(Co). These deposit types exhibit characteristic signatures in geophysical data that can be used to target them. This study employs features extracted from geophysical datasets, such as seismic, gravity and magnetics, together with other geodata, in a computer-based prospectivity analysis utilising Fuzzy Inference Systems (FIS), a knowledge-based artificial intelligence technique.

The FIS model relies on a generalised mineral systems model to identify targeting criteria. The mineral system model includes (1) Primitive, mantle-derived, magnesium-rich rocks (ultramafic and mafic rocks), serving as metal sources; (2) trans-lithospheric faults and chonoliths acting as magma pathways, locally enhanced by varying compressional/extensional tectonic regimes; and (3) dilatational zones of high, fracture-related permeability and localised structures that physically trap the mineralising fluids; along with abundant sulphur-rich crustal rocks serving as chemical traps, providing external sulphur required to form immiscible sulphide melts. Spatial proxies representing the critical processes of the mineral system were mapped from various geoscientific datasets in the form of GIS predictor maps. Features representing deep magma reservoirs extracted from seismic data are used to represent the source component. Meanwhile, features such as lineaments and signatures characteristic of these intrusions from potential field data have been utilised in the pathways and traps components. Sulphide-bearing black shales interpreted from electromagnetic data have also been used to represent the crustal contamination in the traps component.

All predictor maps representing proxies of crucial mineralisation processes were incorporated into the FIS model to generate the prospectivity map. The results show good agreement with the occurrences of known deposits and highlight promising regions for further exploration, demonstrating the approach's utility in targeting CRM-rich areas.